

PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ETHICAL AND AESTHETIC CULTURE OF LEADERS

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Annotation The article discusses the role of moral and aesthetic culture in the activities of managerial personnel, the foundations of its development, the correct definition and development of development mechanisms, the criteria for determining leadership abilities and the culture of managers.

Keywords: managerial personnel, moral and aesthetic culture, leaders, high spiritual qualities, worldview, faith, national self-consciousness of the people, socio-economic, legal, spiritual and educational foundations.

Ethical and aesthetic culture is one of the important qualities in the work of management personnel. Leaders who are morally sound, educated and experienced, who have a deep knowledge of the basics of science, who have a strong belief in justice and humanity can be the owners of high moral qualities. All these qualities come together and lead to the formation, strengthening and development of the society's worldview, faith, national consciousness of the people. "The spiritual formation of a leader is evaluated by his fair, impartial, open, responsible, business-like management, ability to make correct and quick decisions, ability to unite and move people towards the goal, all-round readiness to implement political reforms of today, experience and leadership skills" [1].

The new spiritual spirit that is settling in the new stage of development of the society has also put the idea of spirituality of leaders on the agenda. What should be the spirituality of a leader? What ideas form its basis? In our opinion, a leader's morale must first of all have a high sense of responsibility. What constitutes this feeling? It is formed by recognizing "a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights as the highest value" [2]. In this sense, the first element of the

idea of the leader's spirituality is the appreciation of the person. This creates a great sense of responsibility. "It's no secret that today the spiritual world of some of our leaders needs education. Some leaders are rude to citizens, subordinates, and the public. This also makes us all think the same [3].

The moral-aesthetic culture of leading personnel is a complex system that includes their emotional and intellectual abilities, ideas about a perfect life, and, finally, real things-phenomena and forms of behavior created on the basis of not only natural necessity, but also the laws of beauty.

In this sense, it is possible to point out the following foundations of the development of the ethical and aesthetic culture of the leading personnel:

1. Socio-economic foundations. As observed in all spheres, in Uzbekistan there are socio-economic foundations that affect the development of the moral culture of a leader. In every state and public organization, funds are allocated for improving the skills of employees and retraining them. These targeted funds are formed from the budget and from the income of organizations and enterprises. Also, employees can study on their own initiative in any educational courses based on their funds or sponsored sources. All measures aimed at forming the morale of leaders are encouraged by the state in socio-economic and financial terms. These socio-economic foundations are important in the formation of the leader's spirituality and are bearing fruit.

2. Legal basis. The role of legal frameworks in the development of moral and aesthetic culture of leaders is incomparable. In this regard, there is a sufficient legal framework in Uzbekistan. These legal frameworks are created in accordance with international law and include:

- Constitution (Basic Law);
- Constitutional laws;
- The set of laws;
- Appropriate regulatory documents.

The rights, duties, obligations and powers of the leading persons are defined in this law and regulatory documents. They serve as a legal basis for the development of the moral culture of a leader. Because legal awareness and legal culture play an important role in the moral culture of a leader. The morality of a leader is formed through this freedom. As a result, a person develops an independent thought and outlook. This is one of the first elements of spirituality.

3. Spiritual and educational foundations. There are several types of educational foundations for the development of moral and aesthetic culture of a leader. They are:

- Spiritual heritage of the past;
- Scientific and theoretical resources.

The correct definition and development of the mechanisms for the development of moral and aesthetic culture of a leader plays an important role. In this regard, the most effective mechanism has been created in Uzbekistan. In this sense, there are the following systems that directly and indirectly deal with the development of the moral and aesthetic culture of a leader:

- improvement of qualification of personnel and retraining of their organizations;
- scientific educational centers;
- various training courses, etc.

These frameworks are the main mechanisms of influence that develop the moral and aesthetic culture of the leader. Managers are trained in them with or without separation from work. Thus, in Uzbekistan, the foundations of the development of ethical and aesthetic culture of a leader are purposefully organized. In this regard, the work being carried out is based on a scientific and practical basis.

In our opinion, it is necessary to regularly monitor the spiritual level of the leader in educational and working places. In this way: firstly, it is possible to understand the level of moral and aesthetic potential of leaders, secondly, to develop optimal methods of developing the moral and aesthetic culture of leaders, and finally, thirdly, it is possible to gain clarity in the development of promising programs for the

development of moral and aesthetic culture of leaders. Also, the following criteria are used to determine leadership abilities and inner culture of leaders:

1. Attitude to work.
2. Activity and behavior.
3. Knowledge.
4. Intelligence.
5. Organization.
6. Leadership skills.
7. Attitude towards people.
8. Self-attitude.

The function, duties, rights and obligations of the leading person change somewhat in the transition to the management of the society. This change is significant because of the priority of democratic principles. In this sense, the form of management of the society requires that the leader elevates the spirituality according to the specific traditions and national experiences. Therefore, it is necessary to pay serious attention to three values in the formation of the leader's spirituality. It is presented as a "whole system" whose content is as follows:

1. Spirituality is the intellectual, spiritual and inner strength of a leader who is constantly improving. It leads to independent thought and an independent outlook.
2. Morality is the moral, physical and vital force of a leader. It leads to a healthy body and a healthy life.
3. Enlightenment is the knowledge, experience and belief of a leader. It leads to healthy thinking and social activity.

Improving the moral-aesthetic culture of a leader based on these three values gives these results.

- the influence of the leading person increases in the conditions of social management;
- the leader becomes the most active person in building civil society;

– the influence of the leader in creating social development increases;

Terrible experiences worldwide lead to the following conclusions:

First, if the leader is far from moral-aesthetic culture, totalitarianism and dictatorship will be included in his management style. This, in turn, brings endless problems to the people.

Secondly, the development of the moral and aesthetic culture of a leader is the most effective force and the strongest barrier against evil.

Thirdly, in the development of the moral and aesthetic culture of the leader, he should rely on exposing such evils and flagging human goodness.

If we conclude from the above, material and spiritual values are created as a result of the process of the aesthetic activity of the leading personnel, and the process of his moral activity is a social phenomenon that is an important factor in the formation and maturity of a person. After all, moral-aesthetic culture means not only the desire to know the whole world, but also the social reality surrounding a person, self-awareness of an individual, nation, and society. Because the moral-aesthetic culture is also expressed in the needs and interests of social units, their characteristics, their place in world history, and their attitude to various social systems. Today, the development of science and technology has begun to affect the moral and aesthetic culture of man. Based on this, the role of mass media such as radio, television, internet, and cinema, which create the possibility to popularize and spread cultural achievements, and turn cultural examples coming to the world in different parts of the world into the spiritual food of millions, is very important in this process. But at this point, it is necessary to dwell on the need to have a moral-aesthetic attitude towards the technical means of man. Because it is not a secret to anyone that sometimes a person is not the owner of technology, but becomes a slave, does not use it within the scope of his needs, becomes a source of wealth, a means of achieving his evil goals. We evaluate each new cultural value as positive or negative, beautiful or ugly, based on the cultural values that have been formed in us. In everyday life, each of us comes across different events, we evaluate works of

literature, art, cinema as good or bad events. During such an assessment, the influence of each person's views and values certainly plays an important role. However, in most cases, especially if the evaluated phenomenon belongs to a foreign culture, the value system instilled in our soul by our own culture takes priority.

References:

1. "Democratic society and leadership responsibility in new Uzbekistan". New Uzbekistan newspaper. February 22, 2023, No. 36.
2. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2018. Article 13.
3. "Democratic society and leadership responsibility in new Uzbekistan". New Uzbekistan newspaper. February 22, 2023, No. 36.